

Implementation of the Sustainability Concept

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INTRODUCTION

In 2012 Denmark launched the DGNB certification system. The implementation of DGNB in Denmark is, however, meeting some challenges. Research had focus mainly in the technicalities of the system. But social constraints are also extremely important, and have not been addressed in research. This thesis focused on the stakeholders' perceptions of the DGNB certification system in Denmark. The goal was to understand how DGNB is perceived and how sustainability is being interpreted by different stakeholders. And finally to assess how do that influence the introduction of sustainability concepts in the sector.

THEORY

The successful implementation of the system is related with its acceptance by the organisations that constitute the field. The position of the organisations within the introduction of the system must be carefully understood in order to manage their expectations and needs. The Stakeholders' theory was chosen as the best theory to study the perceptions of the stakeholders.

METHOD

The theory was used in a higher scale than normally used. As the subject of study was the field (Danish construction sector) it was more relevant to assess the perceptions and interests of the organisations dealing with DGNB – in this study defined as stakeholders. The stakeholders' perspectives were gathered through the conduction of interviews. The information was analysed by applying two models of stakeholders' theory: *Framework for Stakeholders' Mapping* and *Power/interest Matrix*, regarding the implementation of the DGNB certification system in the sector.

RESULTS AND CONCLUSION

The interviews revealed that Stakeholders perceive DGNB certification system as the most complete system available to evaluate buildings.

Furthermore, stakeholders stated that the system is complex and time consuming, Because of that stakeholders are addressing the system essentially to evaluate the new building. DGNB is not influencing the building's design in a high level, as it could do. Stakeholders address the DGNB certification system as a checklist. The system assists stakeholders, making sure important criteria are considered in the building. This is not in line with the purpose of implementing DGNB. DGNB is a certification system that should be considered during the design phase of the building. It must be used to support the decision-making process. If introduced in the building design the system could be used to improve the building's performance. This means that, as it is being applied now, great opportunities are being missed. DGNB is a great system to move towards a sustainable sector. However, it is not being applied as its best.

It is my perception that the existence of different interpretations is a result of the overlapping of the stakeholders' interests with the project mission. The stakeholders' interests differ and so they pursue different results from the system. The effort that each stakeholder is willing to make to implement DGNB is not equal.